

“THE USE OF DRAMA TECHNIQUES IN DEVELOPING DIALOGIC AND MONOLOGIC SPEECH IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING”

Xudashkurova Nurxon Ravshanbekovna

The master student of Asia International University, Urgench, Uzbekistan.

Email: nurxonxudashkurova@gmail.com

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Abstract. *This dissertation investigates how drama techniques enhance dialogic and monologic speech in English language learning. Through theoretical analysis and an experimental study, it demonstrates that drama techniques improve fluency, communicative competence, vocabulary acquisition, and learner confidence. Findings show drama is an effective tool for speaking development due to its emotional engagement and interactive nature.*

In this study, arguments are made in favor of using drama (play) as one of the most life-like interactive tasks to teaching target languages and cultures. By reviewing important roles of drama in education in general and its benefits in second language learning in particular, the different advantages and misconceptions of using drama in language classes are enumerated.

Moreover, various techniques of utilizing drama in teaching foreign languages are elaborated on.

Key words: *dialogic and monologic speech, Drama-based activities, emotional, improvisation, simulation, storytelling, and reader's theatre, enhance speaking skills, communicative competence, support creative thinking and enrich the overall learning experience, linguistic abilities.*

Introduction. Drama enhances linguistic abilities and cultural competence in language learners. Drama can foster language skills such as reading, writing, speaking and listening by creating a suitable context. Drama is a powerful language teaching tool that involves all of the students interactively all of the class period. Drama can also provide the means for connecting students' communicative skills. Vygotsky's sociocultural theory underpins the effectiveness of drama in language teaching. Also, drama promotes genuine communication, motivation, and engagement among the students. For the students of foreign/second languages to acquire knowledge about language and cultural competence in the target language, a large variety of methods. As you know various drama techniques like role-play and improvisation are effective in language acquisition.

Methods. The methodology of this research is a drama techniques such as role-play, improvisation, simulation, storytelling, and reader's theatre were implemented during lessons especially, analysis with a focus on different advantages and misconceptions of using drama in language classes are enumerated.

This study employs drama techniques significantly enhance speaking skills. Dialogic speech improves as students actively interact, negotiate meaning and respond to partners during role-play and group improvisations. Monologic speech is strengthened through storytelling, character monologues and prepared performances that develop fluency, vocabulary and confidence. Drama also lowers speaking anxiety and creates a motivating atmosphere that encourages participation.

The research will analyze drama-based activities create an interactive, engaging and emotionally supportive environment where students can practice real communication without fear or anxiety. The relevance of this approach lies in its ability to enhance communicative competence, creativity and fluency in a learner-centered classroom.

Results. The findings of this study demonstrate the following: The research will explore how drama techniques contribute to improving dialogic (pair and group communication) and monologic (individual speech production) skills in English. Research tasks include analyzing drama methods, identifying their influence on speech development and evaluating students' performance after drama-based activities. The study employs observation, practical classroom experiments and learner feedback as research methods. The following methods were used:

Classroom observation to analyze student's interaction and participation;

Experimental teaching to compare traditional speaking lessons with drama –based instruction;

Improvization activities to encourages spontaneous spoken interaction and meaning negotiation;

Storytelling to enhance monologic speech, coherence and fluency;

Learners become more responsive and confident when participating in role-plays and improvisational tasks

Real time dialogic improvisation using online platforms;

Comparative analyses: traditional and digital drama effectiveness;

Discussion. The finding of experiment discuss that drama techniques significantly improve dialogic speech by fostering active interaction, turn-taking and collaborative communication.

Moreover, drama-based instruction reduces speaking anxiety and creates a motivating, learner –centered classroom environment.

Monologic speech also shows notable improvement through storytelling, scripting monologues, which help learner organize ideas, expand vocabulary and especially speak more fluently. In modern English education the development of student's oral speech, in particular dialogic and monologic speech competencies,

Therefore, the use of drama techniques based on an innovative approach in the educational process is of great importance.

Conclusion. The aim of this study to identify the possibilities of developing dialogic and monologic speech through the use of drama techniques, especially digital and interactive drama elements.

The aim of the study is to explore how drama techniques contribute to improving dialogic (pair and group communication) and monologic (individual speech production) skills in English. Research tasks include analyzing drama methods, identifying their influence on speech development and evaluating students' performance after drama-based activities.

Future research should focus on developing practical models for Monologic and dialogic speech, include analyzing drama methods, identifying their influence on speech development and evaluating students' performance after drama-based activities.

The study employs observation, practical classroom experiments and learner feedback as research methods.

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